

The Disinhibited Brain: Combinatorial Coding, and Disinhibition at Axon Hillocks for Human Intelligence and Memory Formation

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Abstract

The human brain's incredible memory and pattern recognition capabilities remain a mystery. This paper explores an algorithmic mechanism, the Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM), to explain how billions of neurons achieve these feats. ADM proposes that combinatorial responses to dendritic inputs occur at the axon hillock, where disinhibition triggers action potentials. This model suggests a simple binary logic governing complex behavior, ignoring subthreshold potentials and focusing on the "on/off" states of axon hillocks. Unlike other models, ADM offers potentially scalable information storage and retrieval through its combinatorial coding capacity. The paper starts with a hypothetical "zero active state" where GABA inhibits all axon hillocks and progresses to an active state representing complex emotions. While acknowledging the limitations of simplifying a complex system, ADM aims to bridge disciplines and contribute to understanding the brain's computational core. Compared to existing theories like LTP, ADM specifically addresses the ability to remember and recall vast amounts of information. While the terminology reflects the author's engineering background, the core findings transcend disciplines, seeking to spark further discussion on the interplay between technology and biological systems.

Introduction

Intellectual capacity is a central aspect of human decision-making that has been studied in various fields such as psychology, neuroscience, and artificial intelligence. This paper explains a possible process that extracts, in milliseconds, the memory of a school picnic from a lifetime of memories. It is a non-conscious, automatic, and rapid thinking process that helps people make quick (Volgushev 2015) and seemingly effortless decisions, judgments, and problem-solutions. It generates a feeling of "knowing" without necessarily knowing how or why. At the same time, human intelligence remains more subjective and less reliable, driven by unconscious biases and emotions that lead to errors in judgment and decision-making. This paper proposes the replacement of the linear summation model (Cash 1999) for the processes at the axon hillocks of 86 billion neurons with an ADM model. The paper suggests that ADM functions lie behind the brilliance and the quirks of the human mind.

The Axon Hillocks

The main elements of a neuron in the central nervous system (CNS) constitute synapses, dendrites, cell bodies, axon hillocks (Kole 2018) and axons. Neurons receive sensory information, interpret them and produce motor outputs through electrical and chemical signals. Primary sensory neurons gather information from the environment and internal organs through photoreceptors, mechanoreceptors and chemoreceptors. The information is relayed through projection neurons to different cortical regions. Somatic motor neurons activate skeletal muscles, while autonomic motor neurons act on smooth muscles and glands. Sensory, projection and motor neurons carry the more significant messages of the central nervous system. Each neuron receives inputs from receptors or other neurons through its dendrites. Its cell body integrates incoming signals for its axon hillock. In 90% of the neurons, their axon hillocks respond to incoming signals by remaining inhibited (Bittner 2017). In the remaining neurons, action potentials propagate impulses along axons towards other neurons.

An Axon Inhibition Mechanism (ADM)

This paper presents a mechanistic view of the mind. It proposes that a simple binary model can explain large aspects of human intelligence. The model limits consideration to just the on/off activities at the axon hillocks of 86 billion neurons. This explanation begins from a starting state for an imagined nervous system, where GABA mechanisms (Compans 2023) have inhibited nerve transmissions. Interneuronal circuits have further curtailed these signals through targeted inhibition. Since activity is the result of an absence of neuronal activity, this paper defines an Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM) as the function that disinhibits GABA inhibition at axon hillocks. ADM is not an

evaluated concept in mainstream science. This paper explains a possible combinatorial coding and memory component to ADM. The paper suggests that protein molecule locks and keys (Filipec 2019) are ADM components that constitute the memory for the imagined system. This hypothesis aims to stimulate discussion and further research, not dispute existing knowledge. By acknowledging the need for empirical testing, we can delve deeper into the fascinating intricacies of neuronal communication and memory storage.

Combinatorial Coding

In 2004, research awarded the Nobel Prize provided strong evidence for the use of combinatorial coding (Gallistel 2017) in the olfactory system. Thousands of receptors in the olfactory epithelium bind to odorant molecules, sending impulses to glomeruli in the olfactory bulb. A single odor activates multiple receptors, and each receptor can be activated by multiple odors. For example, the chemical octanol activates a combination of four different glomeruli, while octanic acid activates the same four plus an additional four. Interestingly, the brain interprets these distinct combinations as an "orangy rose-like" scent for octanol and a "sweaty feet" odor for octanic acid. This finding highlighted the crucial role of combinatorial firing of glomeruli in odor recognition. Similar coding schemes have been reported in specific regions of the visual and auditory systems, like lateral inhibition in the retina for edge detection and ensemble coding in the auditory cortex (Chang 2021) for sound localization. This suggests that it is the actual firing of normally inhibited receptors that plays a key role in the brain's recognition of different odor types and potentially other sensory perceptions. The actual firing of neurons carry the significant messages of the CNS.

The Transmission Of Meaning

This paper propose an imagined ADM to reduce GABA functions at axon hillocks activating axons of individual receptor neurons to enable the CNS to recognize smells. The firing of individual neurons within pathways carries meaning defined by both location and combinatorial relationships. The functional identity of a neuron plays a critical role in the nervous system. For example, cross-wiring between a salivary (Witt 2019) and a lacrimal neuron might lead to crying when tasting (synesthesia). Similarly, cross-wiring between visual and language areas can induce grapheme-color synesthesia, where letters or numbers have specific color associations. Phantom limb pain after amputation results from the brain remapping sensory (Clancy 2019) inputs from the missing limb to other regions. These examples highlight the fact that the individual firing of neurons and their recognition pathways convey meaning in the CNS. The disinhibition of GABA at individual neurons occurs in the olfactory region as well as in visual, auditory and taste regions. By the definition in this paper, ADM is responsible for all these events. The individual firing of neurons and their recognition pathways (Wurm 2022) convey significant meaning in the CNS. The key aspect of this paper is that nerve cell firing requires the disinhibition of GABA at axon hillocks. ADM is defined as the mechanism that achieves this task. Since combinatorial firing and recognition in the olfactory, taste, vision and auditory regions convey significant meaning in CNS, ADM has a role in the conveyance of significant meaning. Failure of ADM would cause a loss of smell, taste, vision and sound in the CNS. Since such meanings do exist, ADM has a role in conveying meaning in the CNS.

The Speed Of Meaningful Processing

The major neural pathways of the CNS convey meaning through neural pathways. Sensory inputs from the environment travel to the sensory cortex. Within milliseconds, the region receives the meaning. Secondary areas integrate meanings from the other half of the body. This integration handles binocular vision (Blake 2011) and stereophonic sound. The combined meaning travels to the association regions. These regions recognize objects and events. The limbic system and the motor regions receive meanings from neural pathways to trigger emotions and motor outputs. Without ADM, the system would be silent. Global decision-making (Faladays 2021) by the CNS can and does occur in about 200 milliseconds. Each of 86 billion axon hillocks receive nerve impulses from about 1000 dendritic inputs and process their On/Off response within 5 milliseconds. ADM is required for them to be On and is not involved when their response is Off. With the aid of ADM, the On meaning can be conveyed globally in 200 milliseconds. This is the typical response time for normal human behavior. If ADM is clarified, ADM explains the speed of the mind.

The Axon Disinhibition Mechanism

This paper proposes the Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM) as a gatekeeper at the axon hillock, (Huang 2018) the decision point where electrical signals transform into action potentials. Its job is to regulate inhibitory signals (GABA) arriving at this critical junction. Traditionally, dendrites (Luo 2016) receive and integrate inputs, but this paper argues that combinatorial computations, where multiple inputs interact to influence output, can only occur at the axon hillock. Take the olfactory system as an example. Here, odor identification relies on deciphering complex combinations of signals from glomeruli, specialized structures processing smells. ADM comes into play by selectively inhibiting GABA signals at the axon hillocks of dendritic inputs receiving specific glomerular combinations. This selective inhibition allows only the "correct" combination to pass through, shaping the final output. What makes ADM truly fascinating is its ability to handle an astronomical number (Iafolla 2018) of potential combinations. With millions of neurons and countless possible connections, the sensory world throws a vast array of inputs at us. ADM, the paper proposes, must possess a mechanism capable of responding to this immense complexity. The mere existence of ADM opens up exciting avenues for research. Uncovering the specific processes involved in this disinhibition mechanism (Letzkus 2015) could shed light on how our brains handle complex computations across various sensory systems. It could also lead to breakthroughs in understanding neurological disorders where these computations go awry. This paper has introduced a revolutionary idea with the potential to transform our understanding of neural computation. ADM, the gatekeeper at the axon hillock, holds the key to unlocking the secrets of combinatorial processing in the brain. By investigating its workings, we may not only gain deeper insights into the intricate language of the nervous system but also pave the way for new diagnostic and therapeutic approaches.

Possible Research Directions

The brain's complexity lies not just in its neurons, but in their intricate communication. This paper proposes an "Axon Disinhibition Mechanism" (ADM) where complex messages are built at the axon hillock, the firing decision point. This aligns with the vast repertoire of B cell receptors, (Treanor 2012) suggesting a shared principle of managing complex information. Could the combinatorial messages, the "language" of ADM, be encoded in proteins at synaptic inputs? Perhaps the symphony of subthreshold potentials, graded responses, and firing rates act as the conductor, triggering disinhibition of GABA at the axon hillock. This dance of excitation and inhibition could then refine the message, shaping neural output. Interestingly, the brain's dynamic nature adds another layer. Neurogenesis (Villalba 2021) in infants creates billions of new neurons, each programmed with specific genetic codes. These codes could guide them to designated areas, forming connections like pre-arranged orchestra sections. Could these genetic codes also provide the "sheet music" for its own combinatorial message, defining the role each neuron plays in the neural symphony? Unlocking these possibilities holds immense potential. Understanding ADM could explain how our brains process complex sensory information, paving the way for treating neurological disorders rooted in these computations. By drawing parallels with B cells, we gain a broader perspective on information management within the body, revealing potential unifying principles across biological systems. This paper explores how the ADM concept extends beyond the axon hillock, connecting to B cells, neurogenesis, and genetic codes. (Liu 2010) By delving deeper, we might unlock an orchestra of possibilities, not just in understanding the brain, but in appreciating the intricate language of life itself.

Conclusion

This paper explores the intriguing possibility of a binary model for human intelligence, focusing on the activity at the axon hillocks of neurons. The proposed Axon Disinhibition Mechanism (ADM) offers a unique perspective on neural communication, suggesting it enables individual neurons to fire by disinhibiting GABA inhibition. While the paper acknowledges the need for further research and avoids claiming definitive explanations, it raises several stimulating questions about the role of combinatorial coding and rapid decision-making in the CNS. However, it's important to acknowledge the limitations of this model. The binary "on/off" simplification may not fully capture the nuanced electrical activity of neurons. Additionally, the proposed role of ADM in conveying meaning and enabling global decision-making requires rigorous scientific exploration beyond the current speculative framework. Despite these limitations, the paper's contribution lies in proposing a novel hypothesis and identifying potential research avenues. Investigating the role of protein interactions, subthreshold potentials, and genetic coding in relation to axon hillock activity could lead to valuable insights into neural information processing. Ultimately, this paper serves as a thought-provoking starting point for further research. While its claims require careful scrutiny and validation, it encourages exploring alternative models and questioning our current understanding of how the brain encodes and

transmits information. As research progresses, integrating this hypothesis with established models and empirical data will be crucial to unlocking the mysteries of the human mind.

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